

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17041847

Improving Disposable Income for Micro Entrepreneurs for Sustainable Rural Communities in India

Vishvjit Thakar^{1†}, Dharmesh Shah² and Farrokh Mistree³

¹Professor and Dean, Computer Science and Engineering, School of Engineering, Indrashil University, Rajpur, Kadi, Gujarat, India;

²Provost, Indrashil University, Rajpur, Kadi, Gujarat, India;

³Professor, Aerospace and Mechanical Engineering, Systems Realization Laboratory, Gallogly College of Engineering, University of Oklahoma, Norman, USA;

† Corresponding author, Email: vishvjit.thakar@indrashiluniversity.edu.in

Abstract: In this paper we introduce the Designing for Service construct to improve disposable income of micro entrepreneurs in the rural India. The Service-Learning Program (SLP) developed by the Modern Higher Education Institutes (HEI) caters to the need of modernizing the business of the micro-entrepreneur in rural India. SLP is to be designed to address the health care sector in the rural area in which people are facing problem of malnutrition, anemia and bedsores. The University Based Support System (UBSS) in collaboration with hospital, public health centre and urban health centre shall conduct survey of the people and address the problem as service learning through nurturing of the students. In this paper a use case of the berry farm in the rural Gujarat, where in the micro entrepreneur works to pick up berries from the many trees in the farm with help of some workers. This, he does with his family. The collection and separation of the berries is done manually. He is plugged into a supply chain for getting his product to various markets. Students participating in the SLP will be tasked to develop smart services and smart appropriate technology to improve the efficiency of the farm. Indrashil's engineering department will coordinate development of automatic plucking of the fruit and classification of good and spoiled fruits on the branch itself. Though the task is difficult and challenging but achievable. Thus, the system studied will help improving disposable income of the microentrepreneurs community to be sustainable. Both cases have been implemented and the outcome is much relevant to the sustainable communities in the rural sector.

Keywords: Designing for Service, Service-Learning Program, Health care, Agriculture, Sustainable community.

Main Highlights:

The key highlights of the papers are Service Learning Program (SLP) and Designing for Service for Higher Education Institutes (HEI) for integrating with health care services and agriculture services in the rural and urban area for sustainable community for improving their disposable

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

income. The University Based Support System (UBSS), University Based Service Learning Program (UBSLP) and University Based Extension Services (UBES) are playing important role in the developing eco system for micro entrepreneur to use the advanced technology in the health care and agriculture sector and it was implemented in the Farms and Primary Health Centres (PHC). The use cases of Berry Farm and Sugarcane vendors for agriculture sector and PCR training for healthcare sectors have been demonstrated as potential benefits for sustainable communities.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors acknowledge the support given by Suman Dantani for facilitating visits to his farms and allowing us to take the pictures. The authors acknowledge the support from Indian Red Cross Society for demonstration on CPR to the Indrashil University Students. The authors acknowledge the Indrashil University for providing the opportunity for carrying out the work presented in this paper.

1. Introduction

As of 2021, the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita in India is 1936.94 USD, which is equivalent to 15 percent of the World's average. The contribution of micro-entrepreneurs to India's GDP is approximately 30%. These small-scale businesses, including rural farmers, home based enterprises, street vendors, and service providers, collectively play the vital role in sustaining local economy and lively hoods. Their impact extends beyond mere numbers, fostering community well-being and sustainable development. Designing for Service is a strategic approach aimed towards maximizing Social Return on Investment in the rural sector by deploying, for example, smart services for water harvesting, water conservation, energy conservation, rural transportation, crop harvesting, supply chain management and logistics for farmers.

Micro entrepreneur in India typically operates very small enterprises with investment ranging from INR 10,000 to few lakhs. These tiny business often relies solely on individual or family labor. Despite their significance, micro entrepreneurs have received less attention and support. They engage in various activities, such as fruit and vegetable vending, thrift clothes selling, tailoring, and animal husbandry. However, they face challenges related to market fluctuations, policy changes, and family crisis. Organizations like SEWA Bharat work to empower women entrepreneurs by providing access to capital, financial literacy and market fluctuations.

The Designing for Service construct as envisaged by Indrashil University, an HEI provides support for starting, incubating, and launching startups for students and rural micro entrepreneurs. For successful implementation we envisage monitoring deployed assets remotely and providing solutions as needed for micro-entrepreneurs in the rural sector.

1.1 Role of Indrashil University in a Technologically Driven World

We envisage Indrashil University leveraging technology and multidisciplinary approaches to enhance the disposable income of micro-entrepreneurs in rural India. Indrashil aims to nurture the student's innovations as well as incubation encouraging startups through their various academic initiatives in the curriculumlike Engineering Innovative Projects (EIP) and Industrial Practices [1]. Herein lies an opportunity for the university community to learn how to create intellectual, economic, and social value and maximize the nexus among them. The focus in this paper is to introduce the Designing For Service construct that aligns with the vision of the Indrashil University. The NEP 2020 calls for nation building by transdisciplinary research and

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

teaching. In the context of nation building, we propose creating an ecosystem within University for entrepreneurially minded and socially conscious students to increase the disposable income of micro-entrepreneurs in the rural sector.

A support system to improve the disposable income of rural micro-entrepreneurs can be effectively designed using a three-tiered university-based ecosystem.

1. **University-Based Support System (UBSS)**
 - Provides direct engagement with rural entrepreneurs.
 - Offers consultation, mentorship, and technological assistance.
 - Connects entrepreneurs with public health centers (PHC), urban health centers (UHC), and markets.
2. **University-Based Service-Learning Program (UBSLP)**
 - Involves students in real-world rural challenges through a "living laboratory" approach.
 - Facilitates the design and deployment of appropriate smart technologies and services.
 - Embeds community-based service projects into academic curricula.
3. **University-Based Extension Services (UBES)**
 - Ensures long-term support through maintenance, upgrades, and education.
 - Provides hands-on training and skill development for sustaining the initiatives.

This tripartite system ensures not just one-time intervention but continuous engagement and adaptive support, fostering a long-lasting impact.

1.2 University-Based Support System, Service-Learning Program and Extension Service

The proposed support system includes a SLP focused on designing and deploying smart technologies that are appropriate for increasing the disposable income of micro-entrepreneurs in the rural sector. It also includes an "extension" center to continually service the installed technology in the rural sector and provide advice and solutions to micro-entrepreneurs. For the SLP the village will be the living laboratory for entrepreneurially minded and socially conscious students to learn how to design, deploy, manage, and maintain services that increase the disposable income of micro-entrepreneurs. The curriculum will be geared towards designing services (non-technical and technical) to increase the disposable income of micro-entrepreneurs in the rural sector. To ensure sustainability of this endeavor, we envisage creating a web portal for sustaining and growing this program [2].

The SLP will be anchored in the Designing For Service construct, with designing services as primary objective and designing smart appropriate technical products as the secondary objective. The extension service will be designed to provide support for starting, incubating and launching startups for Indrashil University students and micro-entrepreneurs in the rural sector. [3], [4].

The village Rajpur at Kadi District serves as living laboratory for the SLP aimed at creating a smart supply chain for a micro-entrepreneur who grows berries and lemons [5],[6]. The fruits collected at the farm are being linked to agriculture market in Taluka and District market place. As IT infrastructure is available within Indrashil University,

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

A web portal will be provided for accepting orders as well as mobile applications developed for improving the business visibility across the country. In the next section we document use cases for implementing the Designing for Service construct at Indrashil University.

1.3 Methodology

Research Design

This study adopts a **case study-based qualitative methodology** using the *Designing for Service* construct as a framework. The selected case studies focus on the agriculture and healthcare sectors in rural Gujarat, India.

Study Location

Two main villages were chosen:

- **Rajpur (Mehsana District)** – For agricultural entrepreneurship (berry farming).
- **Piplav (Anand District)** – For informal sector entrepreneurship (sugarcane juice vendor).

Participants

- Micro-entrepreneurs in agriculture and informal sectors.
- Students and faculty from Indrashil University.
- Healthcare professionals associated with Apollo Hospitals and the Indian Red Cross Society.

Data Collection Methods

- Field visits and on-site observations.
- Informal interviews with entrepreneurs and stakeholders.
- Surveys conducted through UBSS in collaboration with PHCs/UHCs.
- Participation in training programs (e.g., CPR training for students).

Implementation Strategy

- Deployment of student-led Service-Learning Projects (SLP).
- Development of smart services and appropriate technologies.
- Integration of university infrastructure (e.g., IT systems, labs) for real-time support and monitoring.
- Design of web and mobile platforms to enhance market access.

Evaluation

The outcomes were qualitatively assessed based on:

- Improvement in disposable income.
- Enhanced business efficiency.
- Entrepreneur satisfaction and business sustainability.
- Student engagement and skill development.

2. Agriculture Sector

Micro entrepreneurship, agriculture and farming are closely related sectors. Agriculture affects the entire population of the earth and, indeed, agricultural micro entrepreneurs will always be in demand. The youngest country in the world, India, where more than 65 percent of the population is under 35 years of age, while more than 50 percent of the population is under 25 years of age and agricultural education and research in the rural India, can be based on the principle of innovation, motivation and technology driven like web based and mobile based, for those wishing to make their living through

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

agriculture, even if they have the capital needed to break into the commoditized part of the industry. The 21st century is constantly changing the market scenario in all most all sectors. With the development of high-tech business models and the introduction of new technologies, many talented youngsters with creative ideas and willingness to work have been attracted to agricultural micro entrepreneurship.

These micro entrepreneurs and start-ups can generate a fair and valuable contacts in the agricultural value chain and accelerate and efficient delivery of products, technologies, and services to both farmers and customers. To encourage this new venture, schemes like Skill Development, Start-up India and Mudra Yojana [7]. Agriculturemicro entrepreneurship is now a days a major opportunity for the people who lives in rural areas. On the contrary it is also a fact that the majority of rural entrepreneurs are facing many problems due to not availability of primary amenities like IT infrastructure, communication and supply chain in the deep rural areas. It is also observed that the major technical problems, administrative, organizational problems, economic, social and financial problems faced by agriculture entrepreneurs, i.e. availability of raw material, electricity, water supply, lack of training support and labor shortage etc. The Designing For Service and SLP can be very effective under these circumstances [8].

2.1 Use Cases In Agriculture Sector

There are many opportunities in the agriculture sector like Honey Agribusiness, Mushroom Farming, Food Processing, Micro Irrigation, Dairy Products, Fruits and Vegetable Farming, Floriculture Marketing and Cultivation of Staple Food. There are other related areas like selling flowers through the marketing chains in the morning known as flower market place where in the men and women can set up their micro entrepreneurship business. In the section to follow two use cases have been described.

2.2 A Berry Farm at the Rajpur Village in the Vicinity of the Indrashil University, Mehsana District

At the berry farm in the rural Gujarat, the micro entrepreneur works to pick up berries from the many trees in the farm with help of some workers. This, he does with his family. The collection and separation of the berries is done manually. He is plugged into a supply chain for getting his product to various markets. Students participating in the SLP will be tasked to develop smart services and smart appropriate technology to improve the efficiency of the farm. Indrashil's engineering department will coordinate development of automatic plucking of the fruit and classification of good and spoiled fruits on the branch itself. Though the task is difficult and challenging but achievable. In Fig.1 to Fig.4 we show the farm, manual sorting of the berry fruits, the collection and packing them manually in the bag. In addition we have learned that the relatively large in size berry fruit popularly known as "Kashibor" has vitamin B12 in them. We learned that vitamin B12 deficiency affects a large population across the country. We suggest that the UBSS is appropriate for setting up testing and extraction of the vitamin B12. Then the capsules or tablets can be developed and distributed after passing through appropriate clinical and laboratory testing procedures. This can give huge rise in the disposable income of the micro entrepreneur in the rural India by connecting them to the herbal medicine Industry.

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

Figure 1. A View of Berry Farm Figure 2. Manual Sorting of Berry Fruits

Figure 3. A view of Berry Farm Figure 4. Collection of berry fruit packed

2.3 A Sugar Cane Juice Vendor in The Rural Are of Piplav, Anand District, Gujarat

There is a sugar cane juice vendor who has his cart outside a temple in the rural part of Gujarat, India. He is using a diesel engine to power the machine to crush the sugarcane and the juice collected in the vessel. In this case the UBSS can help him in setting up small OFF grid or hybrid solar plant above his cart. Thus, making him contribute to green energy. To improve his disposable income further, an additional system of sugarcane crushing with autonomous drive, can be designed and deployed to increase his throughput of the day.

3. Health Care Sector

There are opportunities in the health sector for micro entrepreneurs. Innovation” whether in the form of digital technologies or business models – dominates imaginaries of global health futures and is often promoted as a “solution” through which the goal of universal health coverage can be achieved. Seemingly disrupting the status quo, it offers the promise of novel and simple answers to longstanding and complex social problems. One of its defining features is an “innovative” financing mechanism based on micro entrepreneurship. There is a scope for young people as health micro-entrepreneurs, who may market digital healthcare in rural areas in order to provide access to affordable and high-quality biomedical care. This mode can promise sustainable modes of financing healthcare; it shifts financial risk to low-income groups who can be micro entrepreneurs. Healthcare can be made accessible and affordable using the Designing for Service and Service-Learning Program for micro entrepreneurs. [9]. There can be role as Health assistants who may cycle around to offer their services; others wait for patients to arrive in the small health center known as PHC and UHC. When patients seek out consultations, health workers and health assistants feed their demographic and medical data into a software program on the web portal, conduct the indicated clinical examinations, and send the completed electronic health record to one of the backend doctors located in the town. After surveying the data, a doctor briefly speaks with the patient by phone before sending their instructions and a prescription through the portal. Located in a village about half an hour

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

from the nearest local train station, the health workers serve populations who face barriers in accessing good-quality and affordable biomedical support. These can be micro entrepreneur deployed to make universal health coverage a reality rural area through “innovative solutions.”

3.1 Use Case of Health Care Sector

3.2 Indrashil University is engaged in healthcare by providing first hand training to the students for CPR in association with Indian Red Cross Society. More than 100 students trained for a day long training session. For Designing for Service for Public Health Centre (PHC) and Urban Health Center (UHC) we propose setting up MedTech program. We envisage Indrashil University working jointly with the Apollo Hospital to understand the need of the hospital and set up MedTech program. Anemia and deficiency of B12 are major concerns for women in rural areas. We envisage Indrashil University setting up the environment to survey women in Gujarat and creating aneco system by involving rural leaders. Further cases of bedsores (pressure ulcer) in elderly people are also observed due to poor nutrition. The health care entrepreneur in the rural area can set up the centre and improve their disposable income. In Fig. 6 and 7 we show the training in the health care at Indrashil University by Red Cross society. This training is a part of the service-learning program and training to develop them as a micro entrepreneur in the health care as a part of saving organization.

Figure 5. Training by Red Cross Volunteer on Floor Figure 6. Training by Red Cross Volunteer on table

4. Supporting Interventions Can Deliver Sustainable Outcomes

Supporting interventions through SLP and UBSS can lead to sustainable outcomes in the

Following ways:

- **Technology Integration:** Solutions like automated berry sorting and solar-powered sugarcane machines increase productivity while reducing costs.
- **Student Engagement:** University students act as innovation catalysts by developing context-specific tools and services.
- **Health Innovations:** Micro health entrepreneurs offer affordable, tech-enabled healthcare, promoting wellness and economic growth.
- **Market Linkages:** Mobile apps and web portals developed under the program enhance visibility, streamline supply chains, and expand markets.
- **Continuous Feedback Loop:** Real-time monitoring and adaptive strategies ensure relevance and sustainability.

These interventions create a self-reinforcing ecosystem where innovation, training, and Entrepreneurship collectively builds a robust rural economy

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

4.1 Building Resilient Communities

Communities become more resilient through:

- **Capacity Building:** Training micro-entrepreneurs and students in practical and technical skills.
- **Diversification:** Encouraging ventures across agriculture, health care, and renewable energy to mitigate risk.
- **Infrastructure Support:** Addressing gaps in IT, logistics, and healthcare through university-driven initiatives.
- **Social Inclusion:** Involving women and marginalized groups in entrepreneurship, especially in sectors like health micro-enterprise.
- **Policy and Institutional Linkages:** Partnering with schemes like Startup India, Skill Development, and Mudra Yojana to strengthen resource access.

By empowering local agents and ensuring systemic support, communities become better equipped to withstand economic and social shocks.

4.1.1 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This paper is a **visionary attempt** to integrate higher education, service design, and grassroots entrepreneurship. It demonstrates how students and universities can co-create solutions that enhance the livelihoods of rural micro-entrepreneurs while fostering socially responsible education. The content bridges theory and practice effectively, offering a compelling model for sustainable community development.

We suggest that the deployment of the Designing for Service construct by Indrashil University will significantly increase the disposable income of the micro entrepreneur in the rural India and also provide an opportunity for socially conscious and entrepreneur minded students to learn how to serve the rural sector in India. The use cases of the agriculture and health sector reveals that there is much scope for working in the agriculture and health sectors for improving the disposable income of the micro entrepreneurs in the rural India. Service-learning differs from other forms of community-based experiential learning such as fieldwork, internships, or volunteerism. It is characterized by the purposeful integration of the service experience into the course.

It entails collaboratively designing a service project with a community partner, selecting course content and assignments that inform the service, and facilitating ongoing reflection that prompts students to make meaning of the service experience in light of the course learning. Designing For Service increases student engagement and fosters increased interaction with students. It creates new avenues for community-based research and scholarly work and increases opportunities for professional recognition. It connects teaching to research and service functions, faculty across disciplines. It enhances academic learning by connecting course content to real-world experience and prompts self-reflection on the student's role as a citizen, scholar, or professional. Designing For Service stimulates increased awareness of frameworks including diversity and sustainability and fosters practical skills such as public speaking, collaboration, and problem solving. It Increases opportunities for mentorship by faculty and increases sense of connectedness to the university and local community. It also connects

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

community partners to university resources and opportunities. It educates students about community issues and engages faculty expertise. [8], [9].

References

1. Astin, Alexander W., Lori J. Vogelgesang, Elaine K. Ikeda, and Jennifer A. Yee, “*How Service-Learning Affects Students*”, Los Angeles, ULCA Higher Education Research Institute, 2000
2. Bringle, R. G. and J. A. Hatcher, *Implementing Service-Learning in Higher Education. Journal of Higher Education*, 67(2): 67-73, 1996
3. C Dienhart, [G Maruyama](#), [M Snyder](#), [A Furco](#), MS McKay, L Hirt, R Huesman, “*classes*”, *The Journal of social psychology*, Taylor & Francis, 2016
4. [K. Resch](#) and [I. Schritteser](#), “*Using the Service-Learning approach to bridge the gap between theory and practice in teacher education*”, *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, Pages 1118-1132 , Taylor and Francis Publication, 2021
5. Seema Jaychandran, “*Micro entrepreneurs in Developing Countries*”, *Handbook of Labor, Human Resources and Population Economics*, pp 1-31, Springer Link, 2019
6. A Bernhardt, E Field, R Pande, [N Rigol](#) , “*Household matters: Revisiting the returns to capital among female micro entrepreneurs*”, *American Economic Review: Insights*, pp. 141–60 vol. 1, No. 2, September, 2019
7. Anupama Verma and P. Shrivastava, “*Scope And Challenges Of Entrepreneurship In Agriculture In India*, *International Journal of Education, Modern Management*”, *Applied Science & Social Science*, Volume 03, No. 02(III), pp.75-79, April - June, 2021
8. D. V. Singh , S. K. Singh and M. S. Meena, “*Agri Entrepreneurs: Problems, Suggestions and Strategy for Successful Running of Enterprise*”, *Indian Journal of Extension Education Vol. 55, No. 3*, pp 138-141 2019
9. Sandra_Bärnreuther, “*Disrupting healthcare? Entrepreneurship as an innovative financing mechanism in India’s Primary Health Care*”, *Social Science & Medicine* Volume 319, February 2023,
10. Service-Learning Course Design Guide, *The University of Tennessee, Knoxville, USA*.
11. Chiaki Hirai; Erika Tanaka, “*Integration of Collaborative and Systematic Approaches for Service Design*”, [ICSSSM12](#), China, 2012.